

Deliverable D7

A set of standards and guidelines for data publication

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Acronyms and their meaning	
Acronym	Meaning
ABCD	Access to Biological Collections Data
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BioCAsE	Biological Collections Access Service
BLR	Biodiversity Literature Repository
CETAF	Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities
DAK	Digital Accessible Knowledge
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DwC	Darwin Core
EFG	Extension For Geosciences
EJT	European Journal of Taxonomy
EVA	European Vegetation Archive
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GGBN	Global Genome Biodiversity Network
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GUID	Globally Unique Identifier
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
JATS	Journal Publishing Tag Set
LOD	Linked Open Data
NHC	Natural History Collection
NHM	Natural History Museum
OAJ	Open Access Journals
PDF	Portable Document Format
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDF	Resource description Framework
TDM	Text and Data Mining
TRY	Plant Trait Database
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

Introduction

The relevance of making biodiversity data open and fully accessible has been highlighted several times, especially since the 1992 Rio Earth Summit, and today it is a major goal of several different initiatives. The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and the Biological Collection Access Service (BioCAsE), addressed the aggregation and interoperability of primary data (field observation and natural history collection specimens data), while other initiatives are addressing the aggregation of other data (e.g. functional traits in plants - the TRY).

As far as primary biodiversity data are concerned there is a relevant gap between observations (i.e., reports from field work) and natural history specimens (i.e., objects collected in the field, and preserved in natural history museums, or other research institutions). Currently, the GBIF is aggregating ca. 2,3 billion records. Among these, ca. 217 million records only (less than 10%) are coming from digitized natural history collection specimens. The ca. 90% are observations, most of which come from citizen science activities. Furthermore, the ratio specimens / observations is foreseen to decrease, since the amount of observation data which are entering the GBIF is skyrocketing, while digitization efforts are, at best, lagging back. Certainly, urgency coming from the progressive increasing loss of biodiversity due to global change fueled the increase of observation gathering, thus reducing the efforts for the intrinsically slower production of new specimens. However, the lag in digitization of the huge amount of specimens stored in natural history collections (an estimate amount is up to 3 billion specimens) is mostly due to the relevant cost (in terms of time, money, and expertise) of digitization activities, if compared to the decreasing resources that museums in general, and natural history collections in particular are receiving. This trend is generating a relevant concern, since the fitness for use of specimens is far higher than that of observations. In fact, several operations - such as falsification of identification, or DNA analysis - can

be performed on specimens alone, leading to a wealth of ancillary data, which can be relevant to several fields of research.

Difficulties in digitization mostly arise from the accumulative nature of natural history collections. They contain units, each with one or more labels, and often with part of their data stored separately in literature, and modern (i.e., ca. post 1990) units only are normally provided with geographic coordinates of the locality of collection. Plus, recent units only have typewritten, or computer prints labels, which speeds up the transcription processes, while handwritten labels call for human intervention, or the application of modern AI approaches (which however require a high quality human effort for proper AI training). Another issue is related to digital imaging. It can be relatively easy in the case of two-dimensional herbarium specimens, or extremely difficult in the case of three dimensional specimens, such as insects. Furthermore, storage of digital images is an increasing problem, which pose the question whether to preserve the images, after they have been used by an AI tool for extracting data from the labels. As a further issue, pre-digitization curation of specimens, and especially taxonomic check, as well as post-digitization curation, such as data quality control, are activities which do require taxonomists' skills. This however should facet issues related to taxonomic impediment. An interesting survey was carried on by the GBIF in 2010, in order to understand why so little natural history collection data are present in the digital domain, which evidenced that the major constraints for digitization of NHC were lack of funding, personnel (i.e., funding), and time (i.e., funding, again).

It is evident that digitization demands for a relevant effort for Institutions, and personnel. In order to achieve the digitization of its collections, an institution needs to invest fundings, and commit personnel in the digitization effort, or to hire external companies/professionals for the task. In general, poor digitization efforts, lacking of ICT and / or taxonomic skills, lead to poor dataset, which have a very limited fitness for use, because of lack in accuracy,

completeness, and/or interoperability.

Given that the digitization of a natural history collection is a complex, and expensive process, it is relevant to properly enhance the value of the datasets produced from such efforts.

Dataset publication

In general, a dataset is a collection of data. In a tabular dataset, one or more data tables host a record for each row, while each column represents a given variable or concept. The data set lists values for each of the concepts for each record. Data sets can also consist of a collection of documents or files.

Once digitized and organized in datasets, data can be made available to stakeholders by mean of several approaches. Datasets can be published in the digital domain as stand-alone data publishing (e.g., data published by one or more persons, outside the scholarly channels), and scholarly data publishing (in which there are proper citation instruments, and some peer-review process). The first approach can be looked at as an easy way of publishing them, in the sense of making them publicly accessible. However, a proper publication of a dataset should expose data to users providing all those information (metadata about origin, owner, curator, adopted standard, license, quality, etc.) which are relevant for their usage and citation. Another approach is that of exposing dataset metadata to users, and allow access and use on demand. Thus, users can require a dataset for a specific use, following a specific protocol and under certain restrictions and rules. This approach was originally adopted in the TRY database, which has now switched to a more open approach, and is still in use in the European Vegetation Archive (EVA), in which several dataset have a restricted, or semi-restricted access.

However, mainstream approaches tend to make data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). This can be achieved by aggregating

data in platforms such as the GBIF, and/or publishing them in the form of data papers on open access journals. The two approaches are not mutually exclusive, since data published in the form of data papers can be also aggregated in the GBIF, or in other platforms.

Scholar publication pipelines assure a certain quality control of the datasets, since there is a peer review process. Furthermore, in aggregators as the GBIF there are several different data refinement built-in pipelines, which assure a certain level of automated quality control to each dataset.

Thus, while it is always true that the more, the better, data published outside properly scholarly publishing pipelines often are scarcely interoperable, non standardized, and lack of a proper peer review. Thus, while their existence is in any case an added value, our analysis will focus on scholarly pipelines only, which can guarantee the highest fitness for use for biodiversity data.

As far a scholarly publishing pipelines, our analysis faced both online aggregators, such as the GBIF and the BioCASE, and journals which publish data papers. In addition, PLAZI approach for liberating scholarly published data was taken into account.

The GBIF.

The GBIF data publication pipeline is a process which starts from taking the data, to properly exposing them to the users.

Aggregating data in the GBIF, by using the GBIF-IPT (Integrated Publishing Toolkit) or other pipelines, such as Pensoft or the BioCASE, means mapping them against a common data standard (Darwin Core, DwC). This step enhances re-usability and interoperability of data. Furthermore, the GBIF has several data refinement pipelines built in the platform, which assure a certain level of automated quality control to each dataset, such as e.g. the taxon name pipeline (evolved in the COL+ project), the occurrence pipeline (which uses some country-specific rules), the multimedia object pipeline, and the DNA

sequence pipeline. The GBIF supports annotations to allow feedback to the original data provider as well.

The GBIF platform is dataset-focused although it does provide individual records as well. While there exist still some taxonomic gaps in GBIF, especially in fungi, it is still growing at an incredible rate.

The BioCAsE (Biological Collections Access Service).

Currently, BioCAsE hosts 40 million records in several installations around the world. It is structured as a true federated database system. However, its underlying MySQL architecture pose limitations as far as the number of records each federated network could aggregate (the limit is in the order of 50-100 million records tops). BioCAsE publishes data as a web service, and permits full dataset retrieval, as well as allowing querying for single records. Thus, potentially, each record could be referenced.

While BioCAsE is used commonly with the ABCD (Access to Biological Collections Data) standard, BioCAsE protocol can support any data standard, and even permit the use of arbitrary XML schemas. ABCD is intended for sharing natural history collection specimens data. It is hierarchical and allows the repetition of certain sub-sections, and its multitude of data elements (988 leaf elements and attributes in the current version 2.06) enable the accommodation of rich information. For items that don't fit in, ABCD features a slot for incorporating schema extensions with additional, network-specific data elements. Currently, two extensions are in active use: The GGBN extension for the Global Genome Biodiversity Network, and the extension for Geosciences (EFG). ABCD is now undergoing a development, which will lead to the third version of the standard (ABCD3). BioCAsE can feed the GBIF by exporting datasets in DwC Archive format.

Among other BioCASE networks, it is noteworthy that the OpenUp! network uses BioCASE to connect 8.7m multimedia objects (images, videos and sound files) in Europeana, the European Digital Library.

The European Journal of Taxonomy (EJT).

Most new species are described on journals without an Impact Factor (IF). As an example, as far as molluscs are concerned, this is true for the 78% of new names. Since papers describing new species are critical, being legal papers that document the legitimacy of names, access to publications which contain these papers is critical as well. The European Journal of Taxonomy (EJT) is a peer-reviewed, international, and fully electronic diamond Open Access journal in descriptive taxonomy in zoology, entomology, botany (in its broadest sense), and paleontology. The journal is endorsed by the CETAF and owned by the EJT consortium (constituted by 10 Natural History institutions and Botanical Gardens in Europe), which finance the copy-editing, layout and online publication of the papers: neither authors nor readers have to pay fees. The EJT is one of the few journals published by CETAF members which are listed in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). Open access does not simply mean “freely available online”, but it is something more complicated, and being listed among OAJ means fulfilling a set of requirements.

The taxonomy-publishing landscape faced different important challenges both structural (diversity and plurality of institutions, journals, and digital initiatives dealing with taxonomy), and operational (lose of taxonomy publishing expertise within the institutions) to target the need to move taxonomy (a complex science) in the digital world where numerous initiatives occur, not necessarily interoperating. EJT was initiated to address these issues and enable public institutions to regain control over their editorial policy, thus promoting FAIR principles of open access.

While fulfilling its role of being primarily a journal publishing taxonomic results, EJT also serves as a model to test further developments for the taxonomic publishing process. It aims at setting up a new production workflow including an *XML-isation* process at the desk-editing level, prior to PDF publication, for producing more confident and pertinent statistics, and more accurate and confident data (human and machine readable). Up to now, the journal has agreed on a template to describe material citation that can easily and efficiently be tagged and processed by the Treatment Bank platform by PLAZI (see later), and thus quickly feed the GBIF. The same approach has been adopted by Pensoft as well (see later).

Pensoft.

Being one of the first proponents of open access and open data, Pensoft has adopted from the very beginning a multiple data-publishing approach, using semantically enhanced, XML based publishing based on JATS/TaxPub, resulting in a toolbox (ARPHA-BioDiv) with several novel workflows:

1. Data underlying certain research results, deposited in an external repository or as supplementary file(s), and linked/cited in the article where these results are described; supplementary files are published under own DOIs and bear own citation details.
2. Data deposited in trusted repositories and/or as supplementary files and described in data papers.
3. Integrated narrative and data publishing realized by the Biodiversity Data Journal, where structured data are imported into the article text and downloaded/distributed from there in structured format.
4. Linked Open Data (LOD) publishing of biodiversity data extracted from various literature sources and converted into interoperable RDF triples in accordance with the OpenBiodiv-Ontology.

The above-mentioned approaches are supported by a whole ecosystem of additional workflows and tools, for example:

- pre-publication data auditing, involving both human and machine data quality checks (workflows 2,3);
- web-service integration with data repositories and data centres, such as Dryad, GBIF, BOLD, DataONE, LTER, PlutoF, etc (workflows 2, 3);
- semantic markup of the article texts in the TaxPub format facilitating further extraction, distribution and re-use of sub-article elements and data (workflows 3,4);
- server-to-server import of specimen data from GBIF, BOLD and PlutoR into the manuscript text (workflow 3);
- automated conversion of EML metadata into data paper manuscripts (workflow 2);
- export of Darwin Core Archive and automated deposition in GBIF either directly, or via PLAZI (see later) (workflows 3);
- submission of individual images and supplementary data under own DOIs to the Biodiversity Literature Repository, BLR (workflows 1-3)
- conversion of key data elements from TaxPub articles and taxonomic treatments extracted by PLAZI into RDF stored in and handled by the OpenBiodiv Knowledge Management System.

These approaches represent different aspects of the scholarly publishing of biodiversity data, which in a combination with text and data mining (TDM) technologies for legacy literature (PDF) developed by PLAZI (see later), lay the ground of an entire data publishing ecosystem for biodiversity, supplying FAIR and re-usable data to several interoperable overarching infrastructures.

PLAZI

A large body of taxonomic data is stored in scientific journals. Over 1.9 million species have been described in scientific papers, about 20 million

species treatments do exist, and ca. 18.000 species are described each year in those journals. However, most of this knowledge is difficult to access. This because of:

- A) Incomplete digitization,
- B) Texts not ready for data mining,
- C) Publications not semantically enhanced,
- D) Published data not linked to the cited specimen(s),
- E) Most data are not open access, and
- F) History of names is not in Catalogue of Life (CoL)

Digital publishing provides a mean to overcome some of these limitations. Taxonomic publications are part of a landscape of links to different resources. These links can be extracted from the articles, thus strongly enhancing them, and transforming them into a source of true **Digital Accessible Knowledge (DAK)**. Furthermore, once articles are transformed into digital objects, they can be cited properly as a whole, or as single parts, e.g., an author can properly cite a figure from an article, referring to it with a DOI. Thus, it is possible to have metrics on everything.

Taxonomic treatments can be considered the building blocks or basic data elements of taxonomic publications, and are very rich in details. All the other elements of a publication are inferred from the analysis and synthesis of taxon descriptions. The descriptions are also the “legal element” of the publication. Descriptions can be further resolved into the basic units, characters in the description *sensu stricto*, and specimen records. They could be enhanced by shared ontologies and gazetteers.

Thus, liberating high quality biodiversity data from scholarly publications can give access to data provided by specialist, allow quality control by scientist, link to taxa and taxonomic treatments, and to related data. Each treatment has its own persistent identifier, and thus can be properly addressed. The PLAZI pipeline allows enhancing taxonomic data, liberating them, and organizing them

into treatments. They are also feed to Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>), where each part of the article has a DOI, and can be cited properly, thus making data FAIR.

The PLAZI workflow foresees the creation of FAIR data by taking figures and other parts out, uploading them to Zenodo, and making them citable, each with a persistent identifier. Treatments have a DOI and can be published as XML files. Furthermore, linking to external resources, e.g. names to GBIF, is allowed. The pipeline is incredibly effective and works well not only on natively digital publications but also with scanned articles in pdf format. This could allow retro-conversion of old journals, and of those journals which are still only printed on paper.

Dataset publication

Publishing means making something public, in a formal way, fit for use, citable, and trackable through an unique persistent identifier. In a certain way, scholarly publications ara a solution to this issue, since they provide each dataset with an identifier, if it is published in a data paper. This is not always true, anyway, if data are published as supplementary materials.

The GBIF currently assign a DOI to datasets which are generated by queries and downloaded. Datasets are stored for 6 months, then discarded, if the data are not reported as used in some research, due to storage issues. However, the storage of the originally downloaded dataset is particularly critical as far as falsifiability of results of a research are concerned. Datasets do change, mostly by addition of new data, but often also for update/modification of existing data. Thus citing a dataset in a repository such as the GBIF could not be enough, and referring to the exact dataset could be preferable.

In this sense, the current policy for assigning PIDs, such as DOIs, to datasets is probably inadequate. Currently, minor changes (which do not include changes in the concepts) are published as newer versions of the original dataset.

On the contrary, major changes lead to a new PID. Thus, it could be argued whether these practices are enough to assure proper traceability of data. Probably, better approaches could be adopted in the future. In any case, uniqueness is the key. If something is unique, it is possible to track it, and cite it properly, and reuse it. Thus, a proper definition of data publishing could be: **publishing data means make them accessible in a formal way, fit for use, and citable through a cluster of unique persistent identifiers.**

However, even if published data fit this definition, there still a further step, extremely relevant, which is their openness. Published data - whichever their format/platform - are not necessarily open data. Thus other relevant questions are: what do we need to make published data actual open data? What is missing to achieve publication of all data as open data?

It has to be noticed that data which are available in the form of a scholar publication in pdf format are not necessarily open, nor reusable. Technically, to extract data from a paper, a pdf must be managed, in order to extract the text, that must be tagged, identifying its elements. These operations are normally impossible to a common user. And this is even worse if the paper is not a taxonomic treatment, but a list of occurrence records. Thus, even if the data in a pdf are theoretically open, and reusable (as far as a license allows reusability), practically they are not open, nor reusable. Publishing papers, and data papers, in other formats than pdf (e.g., XML), makes them actually accessible, open and reusable, non theoretically only, but also practically.

Furthermore, when data are published as supplementary materials, they are normally hardly traceable, since they are normally missing a proper PID. The only digital object with a PID is the original manuscript, thus a dataset in appendix cannot be properly tracked. Furthermore, their fitness for use is normally poor, since they are normally not annotated or documented. Brief descriptions of the dataset(s) in supplementary material are often available in the main paper, but they are far from enough. Datasets in supplementary materials are also hard-

ly provided in a standardized format. Authors normally publish as supplementary materials data in csv, or excel files, without following any standard in their preparation, thus lowering their interoperability. To be fit for (re-)use, fully accessible, and actually open, datasets in supplementary materials should have a proper PID (ideally, one for each dataset), so that they could be citable, and follow a standard.

Open Data and FAIR data

However, even if data are actually published as Open Data, is this enough? Should we aim at FAIR data as the final result? FAIR data must be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Findable means that they can be uniquely identifiable, through a GUID, and traceable. Accessible means that they can be accessed. Interoperable means that they must be structured by following a standard, so that they could be used together with other data from other sources. Reusable means that they are fit for use in other researches but the one for which they were produced.

How can data become FAIR? The first, mandatory step, is that they are standardized, so that they could comply with Interoperable and Reusable parameters. A second step is that they are published (i.e., Accessible). The Findable part is the most tricky one, since published data are not always findable. Findable means that a dataset is identified by a PID. This is not always true, especially as far as supplementary materials are concerned. When published in platforms as the GBIF, or as data papers, on the contrary, datasets receive a PID, thus are fully compliant with Findable.

Thus, ideally, researchers should submit both research papers, and data papers, instead of publishing their data as supplementary materials. This approach would have a further relevant advantage: since data papers do follow the same pipeline of any academic paper, they would go under a peer review process, thus

ensuring a quality check on the datasets, which is not always done when they are published as supplementary materials. In fact the latter are often overlooked by reviewers, also because an expert in some field of research is non necessarily also an expert in data standards, or in biodiversity informatics. Such an approach could allow to go beyond FAIR data, which do not need to reviewed to be actually FAIR. Revision could allow a solid quality control, allowing to improve the overall quality of data available to the scientific community.

The adoption of approaches such as TaxPub (by PLAZI) for recovering data from literature, and publish each part of the original papers each with its own PID, and linked to the original DOI of the paper, allow the FAIRization of data, and a relevant increase in the availability of FAIR data in the digital domain. However such an approach can be hardly applied to data other than those stored in taxonomic treatments. In fact, the TaxPub approach generates a wealth of PIDs for each original paper, each connected to the others in order to maximize traceability. This is not true, as an example, for each occurrence in the datasets which are published in the GBIF. In this case, the dataset only has a GUID, while occurrence data are labeled by an ID, which is unique only inside the dataset, and thus must be always coupled with the PID of the whole dataset. This happens since occurrence data are too many, and assigning a PID to each one is quite complicated. However, especially when occurrences derive from specimens, a PID would ideal to generate metrics for the usage of collections. In any case, data papers should be the direction from now on, while novel approaches should be adopted to recover what was published in other formats till now. TaxPub is an example, and a starting point in this direction.

It has to be notice also that publishing FAIR data is both a technical and a “mental” issue. Technically, there is the need for tools to allow authors to easily perform some tasks on their data, especially to standardize them, and to describe an annotate them at their best. However, “mentally”, it is important to change the attitude of several authors, which often avoid publishing their data because

they are scared of losing control over them. In this sense, data papers are the best solution, since they provide credit in terms of citations, and increase traceability, thus allowing the generation of metrics. Certainly, preparing a data paper requires more effort than simply putting a csv file as a supplementary material in a research paper. This is probably the reason why data papers are not as widespread as they should. However, their advantages to the authors are great. Plus, with a little effort by editors, and reviewers in checking, and validating, they would allow to provide to the scientific community high quality, fit for use datasets.

Dataset usage and citation

Biodiversity datasets available in different repositories are widely re-used - when possible - by researchers all over the world. The GBIF is providing figures on how many scholarly published papers have been produced by using GBIF facilitated datasets. Up-to-date, this figure counts ca. 8600 papers. This figure is going to increase the more datasets are published and made interoperable in the platform. The same is true for other platforms exposing biodiversity datasets. Dataset exposed through EVA (European Vegetation Archive) generated more than 3500 papers, while those in the TRY database have generated more than 400 papers.

However, while datasets published in data papers can be cited quite easily in the “classic” way (i.e. a reference to a scholar publication), other datasets can be properly cited only by citing their DOI. When users download a dataset resulting from a query in the GBIF, as an example, the system returns both the dataset (which contain records coming from one or more original datasets) and a citation (which has the DOI of the newly generated dataset). The dataset is stored in the GBIF system and preserved for a certain amount of time, while its DOI and metadata are permanent. If users properly use the suggested citation, it

is possible to give credit to each of the original datasets which contained the records from which the downloaded dataset was generated. Thus, from a scholar paper citing the DOI of a dataset generated from a query in the GBIF it is possible to give credit to the researchers or institutions which published their datasets.

Citing practices of the datasets used in the 100 papers revised for the study. Colors represent the desirability of the practice, Green: high, Yellow: medium and Red: low.

Taken from: Escribano N, Galicia D, Ariño AH. The tragedy of the biodiversity data commons: a data impediment creeping nigher? Database. The Journal of Biological Databases and Curation, 2018. DOI: 10.1093/database/bay033. License: CC BY-SA 4.0.

Thus, proper citation of dataset usage could provide a “reward feedback” to data publishers. Since digitizing collections is a long and expensive process, Natural History Museums and other Institutions, which host and preserve collections, need to demonstrate that their efforts and investments in digitizing and publishing data actually produce scientific outputs and added value for their collections. Thus, demonstrating that data are actually used by the scientific community (and maybe also by other stakeholders, such as citizen science groups) could be a proper way to stimulate the continuation of digitization and publication efforts.

Furthermore, **the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), as well as DORA declaration, and Bouchout declaration, now take into account data publication as a possible parameter for career progression.** Even if these recommendations have not been taken into account in any national regulation, yet, the general principles on which they are based will become pivotal in the coming years. **For this reason, it is also pivotal to stimulate proper citation of datasets, and to correct malpractices from authors.** The most common malpractice is that of citing the GBIF (or any other aggregator) instead of the actual DOI of the dataset. This provide credit to the aggregator itself, but not to the actual data publisher, thus lowering the total reward feedback they receive for their efforts in digitization and publication.

It has to be noticed that, even if metrics are - or better will be - relevant for career progression, it is also a matter of “good science”. In fact, replicability of results is possible only when original data are fully accessible. In cases in which a research is made using data from several sources, each source needs to be properly cited, to allow for falsification. Furthermore, proper citations allow to access data and verify whether they were actually fit for use in a specific research, or whether they are fit for use in other researches.

Best practices on dataset citation

Two sets of best practices could be suggested, addressing scholar editors and researchers, in order to publish good science, and ensure that proper reward feedback is provided to the institution which make efforts for digitizing and publishing data. Scholar editors especially have the means for checking that proper citation practices are in place in their journals. This is doable, since Pensoft is doing it already.

Suggested best practices for scholar editors.

- A) Always check that datasets are cited with a valid reference o a data paper, or with a valid DOI
- B) Require that all the original datasets which are used in a manuscript are published as data papers, or stored in some repository, and identified by a GUID
- C) Check - or make reviewers check - that original datasets are prepared following a well established data standard
- D) Require reviewers to carefully check that each dataset used in a manuscript is cited with a valid reference o a data paper, or with a valid DOI
- E) Issue major revisions each time a dataset is not properly cited
- F) When possible, issue addenda to correct improper citations in past publications
- G) Stress the point that publication should be part of research data life cycle

Suggested best practices for researchers.

- A) Always cite each dataset in the proper way (or by mean of a DOI, or as a scholar citation for data papers)
- B) Each time a novel dataset is produced, it has to be published or in the form of a scholar data paper, or as a digital object in a proper platform

- C) Always stimulate other authors to properly cite datasets in any manuscript
- D) Publish all the novel datasets - following a proper data standard - as data papers, or store them in some repository, in which they could be identified by a GUID

Stimulating data publication

Several scientists and collections keepers do not agree on the relevance of publishing data, or are not willing to cope with it, since they prefer to hold their data for themselves. In other cases, collection keepers are not willing to publish data since they think they are incomplete (they do not include all of a collection, or only little concepts have been digitized). Often, this perception of incompleteness is related to nomenclature. Digitization does not go in parallel with the update of nomenclature, and the lack of nomenclature update could lead to avoid datasets publication.

As far as researchers are concerned, the lack of willingness to publish their data is often related to the fear that some other researchers could use them to produce research in the original data owner is not involved. There is a sort of sense of “property” of the data, and this leads to a scarce willingness to publish them, at least until they are considered irrelevant, since outdated, or already exploited enough. Publishing data means losing control over them, since data published in open format can be reused by anybody to produce new research.

However, even if data are reused to produce new knowledge without involving the original owner of the dataset, if it was properly published, a “reward” is provided to the original owner in terms of citations and credit. In this sense, the application of proper protocols and best practices for the citation of datasets could stimulate dataset publication, as well as the exploitation of data papers as the most effective way for publishing datasets.

More in general, not publishing datasets is a waste of effort, since data will disappear once a researcher retires. Plus, researchers produce data thanks to the fact they work for some research institution, which pays for their salary. Thus, at the very end, the actual owner of the data are the institution which payed for them.

The willingness to be the first (and often the only) user of the data one produces is understandable, but it is part of an outdated approach to research. If someone has competencies to reuse a dataset in a different way, why not allowing them to do so? Again, scholar editors could have a major role in this change of paradigm, by simply requiring that all the data which are at the base of a given research should be deposited in some repository, and identified by some GUID, as it is done in taxonomy in the case of type specimens or genetic sequences, which must be stored in Herbaria, or in repositories such as GeneBank (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank>).

If datasets are good, they will be highly cited, thus providing a lot of reward feedback to the owner. Again, scholar editors should be in charge of checking that data are published properly, and that they are produced according to some standard, thus assuring their overall quality and fitness for use. Data quality is especially relevant, since poor data quality leads to poor science.

Dataset citations and metrics

Currently the GBIF can precisely track datasets usage, and provide credit to the owners. However, this is possible only when proper citation practices are in place. Again, the role of scholar editors (and reviewers) is of primary importance in checking that proper citation practices are in place, especially when using data obtained from online aggregators.

An increase in the publication of data papers could at least facilitate proper citation of the datasets. Data papers are scholarly papers, and their citation is

more straightforward for the authors, which, in the case of datasets obtained by the GBIF (or from other aggregators), tend to cite the aggregator, instead of the dataset(s). In an ideal situation, at which we should aim, proper citation practices would allow to the GBIF to build precise metrics on data usage. This would allow the GBIF to feed these data to the dataset owners, which could use them to receive credit for their efforts. These data could also be used for career progression, especially when the the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), as well as DORA declaration, and Bouchout declaration will become actual national regulations in European countries. Ideally, citations tracked by the GBIF and other aggregators could be also included in the metrics by Scopus, ISI, or Google Scholar. But again, to achieve these goals, the baseline is to achieve that proper citation practices are in place. Metrics of dataset usage could be also particularly relevant to institutions, which have to demonstrate that the fundings they use for digitization are relevant. This is especially true when institutions are receiving funding from governments, or from the EU. Obviously, this feedback can be greatly biased by poor citation practices.

A step further: Digital Accessible Knowledge (DAK)

Other than data which are natively published in the form of datasets, following some data standard, which allow for their interoperability and aggregation, as well as enhancing their reusability, a wealth of other data exist in the digital domain in the form of unstructured text. As seen in the case of PLAZI (see page 11), text and data mining tools allow to discover and annotate data which are not immediately available. Tagged data can then be extracted and made findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), by depositing them in proper repositories. Treatmentbank and the Biodiversity Literature Repository (BLR), in cooperation with PLAZI, have already implemented such a process, which led to the mobilization of over 25,000 articles, 180,000 images

and 250,000 taxonomic treatments. Once data is liberated from publications, they can be reused, and linked, as an example, to specimens, opening up the possibility to better understand the scientific reasoning leading to the naming of a specimen. Furthermore, the liberation of data from scholar publications allows for issuing DOIs to each part of the original publication (i.e., treatments, images, etc.), thus increasing their citability. Thus, each author could receive an increased amount of citations from the original work, once each datum has been properly mobilized and indexed in an online repository. Ultimately, such an approach could allow the community to promote alternative metrics to measure the impact of research.

In order to make use of this huge growing corpus of existing knowledge in the digital world, data should be available as “digital accessible knowledge” (DAK). This includes data understandable by humans and actionable by machines, both in terms of structure and semantic annotations, based on existing, hopefully widely, used vocabularies.

An example of the effectiveness of data liberation is the workflow by TreatmentBank and Biodiversity Literature Repository, and reuse of this data by the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), as well as the semantic publishing by Pensoft, the EJT and MNHN Journals allows a reassessment of the published record from human-readable article narratives to both human and machine-readable DAK.

For properly achieving the liberation of data from scholarly publications, a set of best practices could be issued. The following recommendations are not to be considered exhaustive, but are an initial set which could be extended.

1. Standard and consistent formats for article metadata and structure should always be used to facilitate data extraction and annotation
2. Specimen records should be structured before publication in a way to make them reusable, whichever the format of the final publication.

3. Taxonomic treatments and the sections within them should be properly tagged by mean of a standard annotation format to streamline the data extraction process.
4. When publishing in XML, taxon names and other named entities of importance should also be properly tagged to allow data mining and re-use.
5. External PIDs to data or name entities should be assigned, whenever these exist.
6. Machine operable links in the form of PIDs should be used to cite not only specimens, but also gene sequences, treatments and bibliographic references.